

EXAMINING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PRIMIPAROUS MOTHERS' ANXIETY LEVELS REGARDING NEWBORN CARE AND MOTHER-INFANT BONDING: DESCRIPTIVE RESEARCH**PRİMİPAR ANNELERİN YENİDOĞAN BAKIMINA İLİŞKİN KAYGI DÜZEYİ İLE ANNE BEBEK BAĞLANMASI ARASINDAKİ İLİŞKİNİN İNCELENMESİ: TANIMLAYICI ÇALIŞMA**Ebru BAŞKAYA ¹, Perihan SOLMAZ ², Emel ODABAŞOĞLU ³¹Uşak University, Faculty of Health Sciences, Department of Psychiatric Nursing, Uşak, Türkiye²Uşak University, Vocational School of Health Services, Department of Health Care Services, Uşak, Türkiye³Samsun Training and Research Hospital, Pediatric Emergency Unit, Samsun, Türkiye.**ABSTRACT****Objective:** This study was conducted to determine the relationship between the anxiety level of primiparous mothers regarding newborn care and mother-infant bonding.**Methods:** This descriptive and cross-sectional study was conducted with 95 mothers who had infants in the pediatric ward of a hospital located in the Aegean Region of Turkey. Data were collected using the "Mother Information Form," the "State Anxiety Scale (SAS)," and the "Postpartum Attachment Scale (PAAS)." Descriptive statistics, correlation, and multiple linear regression analysis were used to analyze the data.**Results:** The study found that 81.1% of participating mothers were aged 18-35, 56.8% had given birth by cesarean section, 61.1% had no experience in newborn care, 50.5% experienced difficulties with breastfeeding, and 84.2% requested assistance with newborn care. The mean PAAS score for mothers was 42.85±4.61, while the mean SAS score was 36.20±8.31. A negative, high-level, and statistically significant relationship was found between SAS and PAAS scores ($r = -0.554$; $p = 0.000$). The significant variables predicting anxiety levels in primiparous mothers were postpartum attachment level ($\beta = -0.264$), financial status ($\beta = 0.210$), and participation in pregnancy classes ($\beta = -0.254$) ($p < 0.05$).**Conclusion:** This study has revealed that as the anxiety level of primiparous mothers regarding newborn care increases, the mother-infant bond is negatively affected. The findings indicate that supportive educational programs such as pregnancy classes and improvements in socioeconomic conditions can strengthen the mother-infant bond by reducing mothers' anxiety levels.**Keywords:** Attachment, Anxiety, Primiparous Mother, Newborn**ÖZET****Amaç:** Bu araştırma, primipar annelerin yenidoğan bakımına ilişkin kaygı düzeyi ile anne bebek bağlanması arasındaki ilişkinin belirlenmesi amacıyla yapılmıştır.**Gereç ve Yöntem:** Tanımlayıcı ve kesitsel tipte olan araştırma, Türkiye'nin Ege Bölgesi'nde yer alan bir hastanenin pediatri servisinde bebeği bulunan 95 anne ile gerçekleştirilmiştir. Veriler "Anne Bilgi Formu", "Durumluk Kaygı Ölçeği (DKÖ)" ve Doğum Sonrası Bağlanma Ölçeği (DSBÖ)" ile toplanmıştır. Verileri analiz etmek için tanımlayıcı istatistikler, korelasyon ve çoklu doğrusal regresyon analizi kullanılmıştır.**Bulgular:** Araştırmaya katılan annelerin %81,1'inin 18-35 yaş aralığında olduğu, %56,8'inin sezaryen doğum yaptığı, %61,1'inin yenidoğan bakımına ilişkin deneyim sahibi olmadığı, %50,5'inin emzirme konusunda güçlük yaşadığı ve %84,2'sinin yenidoğan bakımında yardım almayı talep ettiği belirlenmiştir. Annelerin DSBÖ puan ortalaması 42,85±4,61, DKÖ puan ortalaması ise 36,20±8,31 olarak tespit edilmiştir. DKÖ ile DSBÖ puanları arasında negatif yönlü, yüksek düzeyde ve istatistiksel olarak anlamlı bir ilişki saptanmıştır ($r = -0,554$; $p = 0,000$). Primipar annelerin kaygı düzeylerini yordayan anlamlı değişkenler doğum sonrası bağlanma düzeyi ($\beta = -0,264$), maddi durum ($\beta = 0,210$) ve gebelik okuluna katılım durumu ($\beta = -0,254$) olarak belirlenmiştir ($p < 0,05$).**Sonuç:** Bu çalışma, primipar annelerin yenidoğan bakımına ilişkin kaygı düzeyi arttıkça anne-bebek bağlanmasının olumsuz yönde etkilendiğini ortaya koymuştur. Elde edilen bulgular, gebelik okulu gibi destekleyici eğitim programlarının ve sosyoekonomik koşulların iyileştirilmesinin annelerin kaygı düzeyini azaltarak anne-bebek bağlanmasını güçlendirebileceğini göstermektedir.**Anahtar Kelimeler:** Bağlanma, Kaygı, Primipar Anne, Yenidoğan**Corresponding Author:** Emel ODABAŞOĞLU, Samsun Training and Research Hospital, Pediatric Emergency Unit, Samsun, Türkiye. **E-mail:** emel0545@hotmail.com**Cite this article:** BAŞKAYA, E., SOLMAZ, P., ODABAŞOĞLU, E. (2026). Examining The Relationship Between Primiparous Mothers' Anxiety Levels Regarding Newborn Care and Mother-Infant Bonding: Descriptive Research. *Gevher Nesibe Journal of Medical & Health Science*. 11(2), 153 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20700613>

INTRODUCTION

Around the world and in our country, especially during the newborn period, the mother is the most important person in meeting the baby's physiological and psychological needs (Çırlak et al., 2023; Shrestha et al. 2016). Motherhood brings new roles and responsibilities to women (Öztürk and Erci, 2016). For women who are mothers for the first time (primiparous mothers), the postpartum period is a multidimensional adaptation process that requires adaptation to the identity of motherhood, acquiring knowledge and skills related to newborn care, and taking on increased care responsibilities (Shrestha et al. 2016; Yanikkerem and Göker, 2014). The uncertainties and responsibilities specific to this period can cause varying levels of anxiety in mothers. In particular, lack of knowledge and inexperience regarding feeding the newborn, ensuring hygiene, and establishing a sleep routine are considered among the key determinants of this anxiety (Shrestha et al. 2016; Yanikkerem and Göker, 2014). Studies have shown that young mothers, mothers with low levels of education, mothers with insufficient social support, and mothers experiencing motherhood for the first time experience greater anxiety regarding infant care (Petzoldt et al., 2016; Razurel et al., 2017). A study by Üst and Pasinlioğlu found that both primiparous and multiparous pregnant women experienced moderate anxiety about childbirth and the postpartum period, but that primiparous pregnant women had higher anxiety levels than multiparous women (Üst and Pasinlioğlu, 2015). In the study by Shakarami et al., it was concluded that primiparous women had higher levels of fear of childbirth and lower levels of self-efficacy in childbirth; however, there was no significant difference between the groups in terms of situational anxiety levels (Shakarami et al., 2021). Shrestha et al. stated that the knowledge, education, and income levels of primiparous mothers were inversely related to postpartum anxiety; and that low socioeconomic status and inadequate social support were risk factors for anxiety and depression (Shrestha et al., 2014). This anxiety experienced by the mother in the postpartum period negatively affects mother-infant bonding (Gancedo et al., 2017; Öztürk and Erci, 2016).

In the postpartum period, not only the mother's mental state but also the early emotional bond established between mother and baby is of critical importance. In this context, Bowlby's Attachment Theory provides a fundamental theoretical framework for understanding the mother-infant relationship. This theory suggests that the baby naturally tends to attach to its primary caregiver (usually the mother) in order to survive and feel secure. In this context, mother-infant attachment goes beyond physical needs and forms a fundamental "secure base" for the baby's social and emotional development later in life. The formation of secure attachment depends on the mother's ability to respond sensitively and adequately to the baby emotionally, in addition to physical care (Bowlby, 1988; Arslan and Teze, 2016).

Maternal anxiety may negatively affect mother-infant bonding through several psychological mechanisms. According to attachment theory, the development of secure attachment depends largely on the caregiver's sensitivity and responsiveness to the infant's cues (Bowlby, 1988). Anxiety can impair a mother's ability to accurately perceive, interpret, and respond to her infant's signals because anxious individuals tend to focus excessively on perceived threats and worries. During the postpartum period, concerns regarding newborn care, feeding, sleep patterns, or the infant's health may occupy a significant portion of the mother's cognitive and emotional resources. This heightened state of vigilance may reduce the mother's emotional availability and limit her capacity to engage in warm, responsive interactions with her infant. Furthermore, anxiety may decrease maternal self-efficacy, leading mothers to doubt their caregiving abilities and avoid or feel less confident in caregiving interactions. Reduced maternal sensitivity, emotional availability, and caregiving confidence may, in turn, hinder the development of a secure emotional bond between mother and infant (Daglar & Nur, 2018).

Therefore, anxiety related to newborn care is considered a potential risk factor for the establishment of healthy mother-infant bonding.

Newborn care is a critical process that forms the foundation of mother-baby bonding and directly affects the quality of the bond (Kınık and Özcan, 2020). Secure attachment develops when the mother responds sensitively to the baby's signals. Physical contact through actions such as breastfeeding, cuddling, swaddling, or "kangaroo care," as well as interactions such as eye contact and exposure to the mother's voice, increase oxytocin release and strengthen bonding. These care actions are crucial not only for meeting physical needs but also for establishing an emotional bond. Newborn care is a tangible action demonstrating how the mother responds to the baby's needs. These actions lay the groundwork for the formation and strengthening of the emotional bond between mother and baby, establishing the foundation for the baby to form healthy relationships in later life (Çırlak et al., 2023; Yanikkerem and Göker, 2014).

A review of the literature shows that mother-infant bonding affects a child's academic performance, cognitive performance, and social and emotional development in later life (Güleç and Kavlak, 2015). The failure to establish a secure attachment relationship between mother and baby also reduces the ability to form positive relationships later in life (Erkut and Balcı, 2024). Identifying the factors affecting attachment and development and providing mothers with the necessary support is very important (Özdemir et al., 2021). The mother-infant bonding process can be affected by numerous variables such as the health status of the mother and baby, the number of pregnancies, the quality of the relationship between the parents, intra-family ties, cultural characteristics, whether the pregnancy is planned or not, the presence of postpartum depression, socio-economic conditions, high-risk pregnancy status, and the mother's first pregnancy experience (Loudon et al., 2016). High levels of anxiety, particularly regarding the role of motherhood, can negatively affect this sensitivity and weaken the quality of mother-infant bonding. The study by Dağlar and Nur reveals that maternal depression and anxiety experienced during pregnancy and the postpartum period negatively affect the mother-infant bonding process (Daglar and Nur, 2018). This indicates a strong relationship between the mother's mental health and the emotional bond she forms with her baby.

Although there are various studies in the current literature on maternal anxiety and mother-infant bonding in the postpartum period research examining the direct relationship between primiparous mothers' anxiety about newborn care and their bonding levels is limited (Kınık and Özcan, 2020; Nacar and Gökaya, 2019). In this context, this study, designed to address this gap, aims to comprehensively analyze the relationship between primiparous mothers' anxiety levels regarding newborn care and their mother-infant bonding levels. It is anticipated that the findings of the research will contribute to the structuring of counseling and education programs for mothers in the pre- and post-natal periods.

Research questions:

1. What are the anxiety levels of primiparous mothers regarding newborn care?
2. What are the attachment levels of primiparous mothers after birth?
3. Is there a significant difference between situational anxiety levels and postpartum attachment levels according to the socio-demographic characteristics of primiparous mothers?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the anxiety levels of primiparous mothers regarding newborn care and their postpartum attachment levels?
5. What are the variables that predict the anxiety levels of primiparous mothers?

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Type of Research

This study is a descriptive and cross-sectional study.

Study Population and Sample

The study population consists of mothers with babies who receive healthcare services in the pediatric ward of a hospital located in the Aegean Region of Turkey. The study sample consists of mothers aged 18 and over, who have given birth for the first time, are literate, can understand and speak Turkish, have no communication barriers, and volunteer to participate in the study. Participants were included in the study not during the routine clinical follow-up process after birth, but while they were in the pediatric ward due to their babies' healthcare needs. The study used a purposive sampling method that allowed the selection of participants who met the determined inclusion criteria. The sample size was calculated using the G*Power 3.1.9.7 program to ensure that the relationship between the main variables of the study could be evaluated with sufficient statistical power. Based on previous studies conducted in similar sample groups (Özyazıcıoğlu and Tüfekci, 2009; Ünver and Arslan, 2022), the State Anxiety Scale was designed with a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$, 95% test power ($1-\beta$), and moderate effect size ($d_z = 0.4469548$), and it was determined that a minimum of 68 participants was required. The study was completed with 95 primiparous mothers who met the inclusion criteria.

Data Collection Tools

Participant Information Form

This form was created by the researchers after a literature review (Kınık and Özcan, 2020; Kırca and Savaşer, 2017). The form consists of a total of 14 questions regarding the socio-demographic characteristics of mothers as well as pregnancy and newborn care.

State Anxiety Scale (SAS)

This is a subscale of the "State and Trait Anxiety Inventory" adapted to Turkish culture by Öner and Le Compte (Öner and Compte, 1983). The scale is used to assess how individuals feel at a particular moment and under specific conditions. Accordingly, participants are expected to respond to statements reflecting their current emotional state, focusing on the situation they are in. The State Anxiety Scale consists of 20 items, and participants respond to each item using a four-point Likert scale: (1) None, (2) Somewhat, (3) Much, (4) Completely. Ten items expressing positive emotions (1, 2, 5, 8, 10, 11, 15, 16, 19, 20) are reverse-scored, and the scores obtained from all items are summed to obtain a total score ranging from 20 to 80. In evaluating the scale, it is assumed that those scoring below 36 have no anxiety, those scoring between 37-42 have mild anxiety, and those scoring 42 and above have high anxiety. In Öner and Le Compte's study, the Cronbach's alpha value of the scale was found to be 0.94. In this study, the Cronbach's alpha internal consistency coefficient of the scale was found to be 0.84.

Postnatal Attachment Scale (PAAS)

This is a scale developed to identify attachment problems between mother and baby in the early stages and completed by the mother (Brockington et al., 2006). The scale was adapted into Turkish by Yalçın et al (Yakın et al., 2014). The PAAS, which is a six-point Likert type (always-never), consists of 25 items, with items scored between 0-5 and 17 items reverse-coded. The scale consists of four sub-dimensions: attachment disorder (12 items), rejection and irritability (7 items), caregiving tension (4 items), and risk of abuse (2 items). The cutoff points determined for the subscales are ≥ 12 , ≥ 17 , ≥ 10 , and ≥ 3 , respectively, and the cutoff value for the total scale is 26. In the Turkish validity-reliability study, Cronbach's alpha for the total scale was reported as 0.75; it was suggested that the scale be evaluated based on the total score, especially due to the low internal consistency of the risk of abuse subscale. In this study, the Cronbach's alpha internal consistency coefficient for the total PAAS score was determined to be 0.63. While this value is within the acceptable lower limit, factors such as mothers' susceptibility to mood swings in the early postpartum period and the fact that attachment

behaviors have not yet stabilized can be considered as factors that may affect the internal consistency coefficient.

Data Collection

Data was collected through face-to-face interviews with primiparous mothers who were in the pediatric ward due to their babies' healthcare needs. Mothers were first informed with an informed consent form, and the interview lasted an average of 15-20 minutes.

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23.0. The normality of the scale scores was determined by examining the Skewness and Kurtosis coefficients (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2013). For all scales, the Skewness and Kurtosis coefficients were within the ± 1.5 range, indicating a normal distribution, therefore parametric tests were applied. Descriptive statistics, including means, standard deviations, and percentages, were used to present demographic data and the scores of the SAS and the PAAS. Independent samples t-tests and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) were used to determine the relationship between the mean scores of the SAS and the PAAS and the socio-demographic characteristics of mothers and pregnancy and newborn care. Pearson correlation analysis was used to determine the relationship between the scales, and multiple linear regression analysis was used to determine the predictors affecting the anxiety levels of primiparous mothers. Multicollinearity was assessed using the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) and tolerance values. VIF values were below 10, and tolerance values were above 0.10, indicating no multicollinearity issues (Hair et al., 2014). In each analysis, a p-value less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethical Considerations

This research was conducted in accordance with the ethical principles of the Helsinki Declaration. The study was carried out with approval from the XXXX University Non-Interventional Clinical Research Ethics Committee (date: 02.03.2023; no: 75-75-05) and with the necessary institutional permissions obtained from the hospital where the research was conducted (date: 30.12.2022; no: E-45786011-602.02.01). Primiparous mothers participating in the data collection process were informed about the purpose and scope of the study, and their written consent was obtained. Permission to use the scales was also obtained from the scale providers.

RESULTS

Table 1 presents the distribution of socio-demographic characteristics of primiparous mothers. 81.1% of the mothers participating in the study were between 18-35 years old, and 36.8% were university graduates. 55.8% of the mothers were housewives, and 57.9% had income levels balanced with their expenses. 74.7% of the mothers had nuclear families, and 43.2% had been married for 1-3 years. Furthermore, 82.1% of the mothers had social security coverage. When examining the data regarding pregnancy, it was observed that 76.8% had planned pregnancies, and 56.8% had cesarean deliveries. The percentage of those who did not experience any complications during pregnancy was 62.1%, while 61.1% had no experience with newborn care. The percentage of mothers experiencing difficulties with breastfeeding is 50.5%, and 84.2% of mothers stated that they needed someone to support them in newborn care. Furthermore, it was determined that 61.1% of mothers attended pregnancy classes (Table 1).

Table 1. Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Mothers (n= 95)

Variable	n	%
Age		
18-35 years old	77	81.1
35 years and older	18	18.9
Education level		
Primary school	3	3.2
Middle school	16	16.8
High school	33	34.7
University	35	36.8
Occupation		
Housewife	53	55.8
Employed	42	44.2
Financial status		
Income less than expenses	12	12.6
Income equal to expenses	55	57.9
Income more than expenses	28	29.5
Family type		
Nuclear family	71	74.7
Extended family	24	25.3
Duration of marriage		
Less than 1 year	18	18.9
1-3 years	41	43.2
4-10 years	33	34.7
More than 10 years	3	3.2
Social security		
Yes	78	82.1
No	17	17.9
Planned pregnancy?		
Yes	73	76.8
No	22	23.2
Method of delivery		
Normal	41	43.2
Cesarean section	54	56.8
Complications during pregnancy		
Yes	36	37.9
No	59	62.1
Experience in newborn care		
Yes	37	38.9
No	58	61.1
Difficulties encountered in baby care		
Bathing the baby	18	18.9
Diaper changing	3	3.2
Putting the baby to sleep	26	27.4
Breastfeeding	48	50.5
Wanting someone to help with newborn care		
Yes	80	84.2
No	15	15.8
Attending pregnancy school		
Yes	58	61.1
No	37	38.9

The mean SAS score of primiparous mothers was 36.20±8.31; and the mean PAAS score was 42.85±4.61. According to the correlation analysis, a negative and highly significant

correlation was found between the SAS scale scores and the PAAS scale scores of the mothers ($r = -0.554$; $p=0.000$) (Table 2).

Table 2. Mean Total Scores And Correlations Of Mothers On The SAS And PAAS Scales (n=95)

Scale	N	Mean±SD	Values that can be obtained from scales.		Correlations *
			Min.	Max.	
SAS	95	36.20±8.31	20.00	58.00	
PAAS	95	42.85±4.61	34.00	57.00	
SAS-PAAS	95				$r = -0.554$; $p=0.000$

SD=Standard Deviation; Min= Minimum; Max= Maximum $r=$ Kolerasyon, *Pearson Kolerasyon

This study compared the SAS and PAAS scores of primiparous mothers according to their socio-demographic characteristics. Mothers who attended prenatal classes had a mean SAS score of 37.86 ± 8.48 , which was statistically significantly higher than those who did not attend ($t=2.506$; $p=0.014$). However, participation in prenatal classes did not have a significant effect on PAAS scores ($t=-0.021$; $p=0.984$). When evaluated in terms of financial status, primiparous mothers whose income was less than their expenses had significantly higher scores on both the SAS and the PAAS compared to other groups ($p<0.05$). In terms of other socio-demographic variables, there was no statistically significant difference between the SAS and PAAS scores of primiparous mothers ($p>0.05$) (Table 3).

Table 3. Comparison of Mothers' Socio-Demographic Characteristics With Their Mean Scores on The SAS and The PAAS (n= 95)

Variable	SAS Mean±SD	PAAS Mean±SD
Age		
18-35 years old	35.79±7.96	42.87±4.26
35 years and older	37.94±9.72	42.77±5.99
Statistical analysis/p-value	$t=-0.988$ $p=0.326$	$t=0.076$ $p=0.939$
Education level		
Primary school	39.66±9.01	43.00±2.64
Secondary school	35.50±7.34	42.43±3.48
High school	37.60±9.37	43.57±5.43
University	35.51±7.80	42.51±4.72
Statistical analysis/p-value	$F=0.655$ $p=0.625$	$F=0.324$ $p=0.861$
Occupation		
Housewife	36.56±7.95	42.83±4.42
Employed	35.73±8.82	42.88±4.88
Statistical analysis/p-value	$t=0.480$ $p=0.632$	$t=0.053$ $p=0.958$
Financial status		
Income less than expenses	41.75±8.89 ^a	45.91±5.61 ^a
Income equal to expenses	36.45±8.11 ^{ab}	43.21±4.56 ^{ab}
Income more than expenses	33.32±7.38 ^b	40.82±3.27 ^b
Statistical analysis/p-value	$F=4.720$ $p=0.011$	$F=6.155$ $p=0.003$
Family type		
Nuclear family	36.23±8.37	42.83±4.76
Extended family	36.08±8.31	42.91±4.20
Statistical analysis/p-value	$t=0.079$ $p=0.937$	$t=0.078$ $p=0.938$
Duration of marriage		
Less than 1 year	38.38±7.42	43.44±4.96
1-3 years	34.65±7.90	42.48±4.36
4-10 years	36.51±9.32	43.15±4.96
More than 10 years	40.66±4.16	41.00±1.00

Statistical analysis/p-value	F=1.197 p=0.316	F=0.385 p=0.764
Social security		
Yes	35.57±8.49	42.82±4.76
No	39.05±6.98	43.00±3.95
Statistical analysis/p-value	t=-1.576 p=0.118	t=-0.145 p=0.885
Planned pregnancy?		
Yes	35.58±8.10	42.75±4.57
No	38.22±8.86	43.18±4.80
Statistical analysis/p-value	t= -1.309 p=0.194	t=-0.381p=0.704
Method of delivery		
Normal	37.92±7.55	42.87±4.88
Cesarean section	34.88±8.69	42.83±4.32
Statistical analysis/p-value	t=1.784 p=0.078	t=0.047 p=0.963
Complications during pregnancy		
Yes	35.66±8.14	43.16±4.42
No	36.52±8.47	42.66±4.74
Statistical analysis/p-value	t=-0.486 p=0.628	t=0.517 p=0.606
Experience with newborn care		
Yes	37.13±9.33	43.21±5.08
No	35.60±7.62	42.62±4.30
Statistical analysis/p-value	t=0.874 p=0.384	t=0.612 p=0.542
Difficulties encountered in baby care		
Bathing	36.61±7.13	42.38±3.38
Diaper changing	33.66±9.07	40.66±9.07
Putting the baby to sleep	38.96±10.12	43.73±6.30
Breastfeeding	34.70±7.41	42.68±3.57
Statistical analysis/p-value	F=1.608 p=0.193	F=0.613 p=0.608
Wanting someone to help with newborn care		
Yes	35.67±8.57	43.08±4.79
No	39.00±6.31	41.60±3.29
Statistical analysis/p-value	t=-1.429 p=0.156	t=1.149 p=0.253
Attending pregnancy school		
Yes	37.86±8.48	42.84±4.86
No	33.59±7.42	42.86±4.23
Statistical analysis/p-value	t=2.506 p=0.014	t=-0.021 p=0.984

F= One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), t= independent sample t-test p<0.05. SAS: State Anxiety Scale, PAAS: Postnatal Attachment Scale Different superscript letters indicate statistically significant differences between groups according to the Tukey HSD post-hoc test (p < 0.05).

In line with the findings in Table 3, a multiple linear regression analysis was performed to determine the combined effects of variables causing differences in anxiety levels among primiparous mothers. The analysis revealed that the most significant variables predicting anxiety levels in primiparous mothers were Postpartum attachment level ($\beta = -0.264$), financial status ($\beta = 0.210$), and participation in prenatal classes ($\beta = -0.254$) ($p < 0.05$) (Table 4).

Table 4. Predictors Affecting Mothers' Anxiety Levels (n=95)

Independent variables	B	E	Beta (β)	t	p	F	Model (p)	R ²	Durbin Watson
Constant	27.792	9.320		2.982	0.004	8.38	0.000	0.19	1.924
PAAS	-0.476	0.178	-0.264	2.669	0.009				
Financial status	2.777	1.305	0.210	-2.127	0.036				
Attending pregnancy school	4.35	1.576	-0.254	-2.732	0.008				

SE: standard error of coefficient. β : standardized regression coefficient. R²: proportion of variation in the dependent variable explained by regression model. p: the level of statistical significance. *p < 0.05 **p < 0.001

DISCUSSION

According to the research results, it was determined that the vast majority of primiparous mothers (81.1%) were between 18-35 years old and 36.8% were university graduates. This finding indicates that young mothers with relatively high levels of education may be in an advantageous position in acquiring knowledge and skills related to newborn care. The literature also states that the education level of mothers is significantly related to newborn care (Khandan et al., 2018). In the study conducted by Öz, Seven, and İreyül on 352 primiparous mothers, it was found that mothers who were university graduates, breastfeeding their babies, receiving support from their spouses, working, and whose spouses were civil servants had high levels of attachment to their babies and low rates of postpartum depression (Öz et al., 2024). However, the fact that 61.1% of the mothers participating in the study stated that they had no experience in newborn care suggests that this advantage may not always be sufficient and that the lack of experience in mothers may increase anxiety (Öz et al., 2024; Petzold et al., 2016; Yanikkerem et al., 2014).

Considering that 55.8% of the mothers were housewives and 57.9% had an equal income-expenditure balance, it can be said that economic status and working conditions may affect anxiety and attachment processes in newborn care. In the study, it was determined that 82.1% of the mothers had social security and 76.8% had planned pregnancies. Similar results were found in the study conducted by Engin and Akyıldız (Engin and Akyıldız, 2021). It has been reported in the literature that mothers with social security and planned pregnancies may have increased awareness levels regarding care processes and decreased anxiety (Ayete-Nyampong and Udofia, 2020). This suggests that these two factors may have an effect on reducing the mother's anxiety level and strengthening attachment.

The study found that 56.8% of mothers had cesarean births and 50.5% experienced difficulties with breastfeeding. Some studies have found that mothers who gave birth vaginally have higher levels of attachment than those who gave birth by cesarean section (Engin and Ayyıldız, 2021). It is thought that the attachment level is higher in vaginal births due to the early contact between the mother and the baby. Breastfeeding difficulties, on the other hand, can increase the mother's anxiety level both physically and psychologically (Altay and Sarialioğlu, 2024).

The study shows that the high percentage (84.2%) of mothers requesting help in newborn care indicates that mothers experience loneliness or need support during the care process. Similarly, in the study by Karaaslan and Akın 71.1% of primiparous mothers felt confident in their infant care before birth, while this rate increased to 95.5% after birth, indicating that mothers needed help in infant care (Karaaslan and Akın, 2024). This result once again highlights the importance of social support mechanisms in the mother's care process.

In the study, mothers' total score on the PAAS was calculated as 42.85 ± 4.61 . This finding, being above the 26 cutoff points recorded for the overall total of PAAS, indicates that mothers generally carry a risk of attachment disorder or experience attachment problems in the postpartum period. The literature states that the level of postpartum bonding is affected by many factors such as the mother's psychological state, social support, and experiences related to baby care (Özdemir et al., 2021; Petzold et al., 2016; Yanikkerem et al., 2014). In the study by Altay and Sarialioğlu, which investigated the effect of infant calming training given to primiparous mothers on mother role perception, maternal bonding, and breastfeeding self-efficacy, it was revealed that infant calming training for primiparous mothers improved mother role perception, maternal bonding, breastfeeding self-efficacy, and extended the sleep duration of babies (Altay and Sarialioğlu, 2024). It is known that anxiety levels play a decisive role in the bonding process of primiparous mothers in particular during childbirth (Kınık and Özcan, 2020). In a study conducted by Motegi et al. with 2379 Japanese mothers (1116 primiparous and 1263 multiparous), it was concluded that Japanese primiparous mothers exhibited weaker mother-

infant bonding and more pronounced anxiety and depression symptoms in the postpartum period compared to multiparous mothers (Motegi et al, 2020). The fact that the mean SAS score of mothers was determined as 36.20 ± 8.31 indicates that mothers have moderate anxiety levels in the postpartum period. Karaaslan and Akin revealed that primiparous mothers experience moderate anxiety and that this anxiety negatively affects their readiness for newborn hygienic care (Karaaslan and Akin, 2024).

According to the correlation analysis, a negative and highly significant relationship was found between the SAS and the PAAS scores ($r = -0.554$; $p = 0.000$). This finding indicates that higher maternal anxiety levels are associated with lower postpartum attachment levels. Similarly, the literature states that high anxiety levels in mothers have been reported to be associated with weaker emotional attachment to the baby and poorer attachment outcomes (Karaaslan and Akin, 2024; Motegi et al., 2020). This result reveals that the attachment process is affected not only by biological but also by psychological processes. In particular, it may be suggested that anxiety related to newborn care among primiparous mothers is associated with lower levels of mother-infant attachment. However, due to the cross-sectional nature of the study, no causal inference can be made regarding the direction of this relationship. It is thought that factors such as lack of experience in newborn care, breastfeeding difficulties, and insufficient social support can increase this anxiety (Altay and Sarialioğlu, 2024; Petzold et al., 2016; Yanikkerem et al., 2014). Conversely, the study by Mutlu et al. shows that primiparous mothers have statistically higher Maternal Attachment Scale scores than multiparous mothers. Anxiety levels were significantly higher in mothers of babies of the opposite sex, while no significant relationship was found between maternal age, duration of marriage, anxiety level, and attachment score (Mutlu et al., 2015).

The study found that primiparous mothers who attended prenatal classes had higher levels of anxiety regarding newborn care compared to those who did not, suggesting that the effect of prenatal classes on anxiety may vary depending on context and content. Systematic reviews report that prenatal education can reduce fear/anxiety related to childbirth in most studies; however, the effect, especially on postpartum outcomes, may be less consistent (Athinaidou et al., 2024). This indicates that the psychological effects of prenatal education on the postpartum period may be heterogeneous. In this context, the co-occurrence of higher anxiety levels with participation in prenatal classes can be evaluated with possible explanations such as selection bias, the risk-focused presentation of the education, individual anxiety tendencies, or the preference of more anxious mothers for the program. Indeed, the literature reports that women with high levels of anxiety may be more likely to participate in prenatal education programs (Athinaidou et al., 2024). This finding suggests that pregnancy school programs should not only provide information but also include anxiety management and emotional support components in a structured manner.

The regression analysis demonstrated a significant association between postpartum attachment and anxiety levels. Mothers with higher attachment scores tended to report lower anxiety levels. However, given the cross-sectional design of the study, the directionality and causality of this relationship cannot be determined. The consistent relationship between maternal distress and attachment problems in numerous studies supports this interpretation (O'Dea et al., 2025). The positive prediction of anxiety by financial status is consistent with evidence showing that economic difficulties are a risk factor for postpartum anxiety and that variables such as income level and attachment can be associated with postpartum anxiety (Ogallar et al., 2025). The prediction of anxiety by participation in prenatal classes suggests that the effect of prenatal education may vary depending on the content and implementation of the program; in some contexts, it may reduce anxiety while yielding more variable results in postpartum outcomes. Therefore, it is recommended that such programs be structured to include psychosocial support and coping skills components while maintaining risk-related information.

Although the regression model was statistically significant, it explained only 18.9% of the variance in anxiety levels ($R^2 = 0.189$). This finding suggests that postpartum attachment, financial status, and participation in prenatal classes are important predictors of anxiety; however, a substantial proportion of the variance remains unexplained. Maternal anxiety is a multifactorial phenomenon that may also be influenced by other psychological, social, familial, and environmental factors not included in the present model. Therefore, the findings should be interpreted with caution, and future studies should examine additional variables to achieve a more comprehensive understanding of anxiety among primiparous mothers.

Limitations

This study has some limitations. Firstly, the descriptive and cross-sectional design of the research does not allow for causal inferences to be made regarding the relationships between anxiety related to newborn care and postnatal attachment. The fact that the research was conducted in a single hospital and with a purposive sampling method limits the generalizability of the findings. The fact that the data were collected with self-report measurement tools carries the risk of social desirability bias and recall bias.

CONCLUSION

This study investigated the relationship between anxiety levels regarding newborn care and mother-infant bonding in primiparous mothers. The findings indicate that mothers exhibit a moderate level of bonding in the postpartum period and that anxiety levels are significantly associated with mother-infant bonding. A negative and highly significant correlation was found between mothers' anxiety levels and their postpartum bonding levels. This finding suggests that higher anxiety levels are associated with lower mother-infant bonding levels among primiparous mothers.

Considering the observed association between anxiety and mother-infant bonding, educational programs on newborn care, breastfeeding, infant soothing, and the maternal role may be beneficial for primiparous mothers. In addition, postpartum counseling and support services should be strengthened by healthcare professionals, and breastfeeding counseling should be expanded. Routine screening for postpartum anxiety and depression may help identify mothers who could benefit from additional support. Furthermore, periodic follow-up programs may contribute to monitoring and supporting mothers throughout the postpartum period.

However, because the study employed a cross-sectional design, the findings should be interpreted as indicating an association rather than a causal relationship. Longitudinal and prospective studies are needed to clarify the temporal and causal nature of the relationship between maternal anxiety and mother-infant bonding.

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Conflict of Interest

There is no conflict of interest regarding the research.

Author Contributions

Plan, design: EB, PS, EO Material, methods and data collection: EB, PS Data analysis and comments: EB Writing and corrections: EB, PS, EO

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